

The Infinite Whole, Finite Universes and Nested Observers Within Them: My Take on Objective Reality

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The Infinite Whole

The infinite whole is a un-contained mathematical space where there are an infinite number of possible states for an infinite number of degrees of freedom. This can be seen as somewhat of a “parent space” to the quantum mechanics concept of “Hilbert Space”. For this reason the infinite whole is infinite simply because it must expand infinitely in an infinite number of dimensions and never be able to have any of its dimensional eigenstates contained in a closed set. Obviously this is because if there was a set that contained an infinite amount of entities, such a set could never be *contained* since it would need to be constantly expanding.

Furthermore, the infinite whole can have no separations inside of it objectively since any separations within any entity must be a result of an observer mentally “breaking that entity” down into a summation of its parts relative to a certain perspective. For example, anything that exists objectively on its own would simply exist as the whole thing that it is. Only when such an object is measured can it be “broken down” into a number of components. As the infinite whole must contain any such observer, it cannot be objectively as a whole separated (since the observer must be inside of it in order to mentally conceive of it and therefore break down its part). It could therefore not have any objective separations and therefore must always be whole hence the term “infinite whole”.

Separations within the Infinite Whole

However, within the infinite whole there could be separated entities if observers observe such entities relative to themselves and thereby “separate” them subjectively. This means that while the infinite whole objectively has no parts, from the perspective of entities inside of it there could be “parts” of the infinite whole that do have parts. For example, if the infinite whole can be thought of as an “open space” that expands infinitely in every possible direction, within that open space there can be an observer. This observer then can then observe what surrounds it within the infinite whole. This means that to the observer, the surroundings are “real” and have separations within them and have real entities with real information that exist within those separations. This is the source of finiteness - as observers have a limited “informational reach” they cannot conceive of all information at once and therefore could only view a portion of the infinite whole that is “in proximity” to them.

The observer can only have a world that contains information (or amalgamations of eigenstates of the infinite whole) that are within the reach of what they could interact with. If information is outside the reach of what the observer can interact with it does not exist in that observers world.

Minkowski's Light Cone

This concept of individual observers having worlds that are only reachable to them can be conceived of by a schematic entitled Minkowski's light cone. In Minkowski's light cone, an observer's potential past and future positions in space are mapped out according to how far they could interact with based on their current position in space and the constant speed of light. Considering an observer could never travel faster than the speed of light in terms of their velocity, there is essentially a "limited world" of space that the observer can reach based on their current position. If there is a point in space that is farther than the distance of the "speed of light" from the observer then the observer could never travel there. This would mean that such a point wouldn't exist in the observer's world.

This shows how in this universe, the speed of light defines the maximum speed at how quickly an entity can ever travel in space relative to time. More importantly though it defines how quickly information can travel. For if information was able to travel faster than the speed of light then there would be temporal paradoxes such as an event B in the future affecting an event A in the past. This is because traveling faster than the speed of light would "curve" the observer's world line and cause them to "interact with entities" back in time. The following schematics show how an entity can travel through time based on their velocity. In the first schematic, the entity is still and therefore would be moving directly through the dimension of time in a 180 degree line. In the second schematic, the entity is traveling at light speed and therefore remains at the same point in time as long as they are traveling at light speed. In the third schematic the entity is traveling faster than the speed of light and therefore has a world line that curves causing the entity to travel backwards in time.

The Speed of Light and Causality

Having a maximum limit of the speed of light therefore not only stops “retro-causality” but also defines the “limits” of the universe. For if entities can essentially “interact” with other entities that are backwards in time relative to the first entity, then the entity could essentially change its “current” state by traveling back into its past resulting in a paradox. An example of this is the famous “grandfather paradox” where a time traveller travels back in time to kill his own grandfather that results in him never being born and existing himself. I would argue that “causality” itself is a result of the speed of light maximum for changing states of information in this universe. Therefore what “defines” this universe is causality which itself is based on the maximum speed of information which is the speed of light.

Why it is Impossible for Any Entity in this Universe to travel at infinite speed of faster than the speed of light?

In terms of why it is impossible for entities to travel at an infinite speed within our universe think of the following example: Anything traveling infinitely fast through a specified set of dimensions can be at essentially at all possible positions within said dimension at once. This is because if an entity travels infinitely fast then the entity can travel from point a to point b in 0 time. This can be seen by plugging infinite speed into the formula for velocity - $V = \text{change in distance} / \text{change in time}$. If velocity is infinite, then the change in time must be equal to 0. This means that anything traveling at infinite speed from point a to point b reaches its destination without any change in time.

Using this logic, any entity traveling at infinite speed can essentially travel “anywhere” within the same moment without any time having passed. This means that such an entity can travel distances A, B or A+B in 0 time. Since 0 time passes the entity can essentially make any number of trips within that same moment meaning that within that moment it can be said to be at “all possible positions at once” in the specified dimensional topology. This is because if such an entity was ever measured it could not be determined where the entity actually existed at the time that it was measured, since in the moment it was measured it could be at any possible position since it is capable of making trips in 0 time.

Information Propagation and the Schrodingers Equation

In this universe relative to observers, entities cannot travel at infinite speeds simply because they do have defined finite positions and eigenstates. For if entities would be able to be “anywhere at once” then the Schrodinger’s equation which predicts the probability of a particles measured eigenstates based on a number of existing factors relating to the particle wouldn’t be possible. This means that within this universe, it is possible for entities to have a number of possible eigenstates they could be measured as, however that number is not infinite. This number of eigenstates that a particle could be measured at is dependent on factors relating to the particle and not completely random as it would be if the particle could change eigenstates at infinite speed.

More interestingly perhaps the number of eigenstates for a particle is perhaps proportional to the constraints of the speed of light maximum. This is because any eigenstate for an entity's property is essentially simply "information". Information itself can only "change" according to the constraints of the speed of light. Again, if information was able to "change" states faster than the speed of light this would result in retro-causality and temporal paradoxes which aren't observed in this universe. This universe is essentially "defined" by causality and "events" which only make sense given a speed of light maximum for changes in information.

This means that a potential particles state cannot be "anything at once" prior to measurement, but rather is dependent on known information and the states of other entities it can interact with. This can be seen as similar to how observers in the light cone can only interact with other entities within a "speed of light" range from them. The particle (or information) in this case can only be measured as having properties that are related to interactions with other particles within a light speed distance from them. This ultimately defines the parameters inserted into the schrodinger's equation in order to determine the probability for a particles measured eigenstates.

What is the Universe?

The universe is a "context". As a bit of background, the objective infinite whole can be compared to an infinite block of informational content with an infinite number of degrees of freedom and infinite number of eigenstates for those degrees of freedom. The universe itself can be defined as a subjective entity within it or a "context" within that content. For example, if the infinite whole can be compared to country, a universe can be compared to the subjective "observations" of a person within that country based on the amount of information said person in the country can interact with. The persons observations are therefore not objectively the country itself but a "way of looking at parts of the country". This is what a universe is - a context of the content of the infinite whole.

Now since objectively there is only a "separation-less" infinite whole, how can there even be contexts or separations within it. Firstly, the position of a universe within the infinite whole would need to exist completely subjectively. This is because since the infinite whole has no borders and expands infinitely in every possible "dimension", the universe's "position" and existence within the infinite whole would need to be entirely subjectively based and not have an "objective" position or topology within it. Furthermore, since the universe itself has separations this must mean that there is an observer necessary to essentially "separate" the universe from the infinite whole by observing. This would suggest that the universe itself as a whole is an "observation" of a grander observer.

The universe can however be more carefully defined as a "contextual finite block" within the infinite whole, since it is a subjective finite thing that exists and not an infinite thing. Moreover, what essentially defines the universe is its size and the fact that it can only contain a LIMITED amount of information within it. This "limitedness" of information is essentially what causes a "speed of light" maximum rate of change for information within it. This is because if there are a "limited" finite number of eigenstates for informational entities, then such entities cannot "change" infinitely fast but rather can only change states into a finite number of potential eigenstates. This "finiteness" of entities states is essentially proportional to the speed of light and

is what allows there to be causality within the universe. The universe can ultimately then be described as a “causally dependent series of information that changes at a rate proportional to the total amount of information inside of it (which happens to be the speed of light)”.

The Infinite Whole
- no borders,
unlimited amount
of degrees of
freedom and
eigenstates

The Universe - limited container of
finite information. This means
there are only a finite amount of
degrees of freedom and finite
amount of eigenstates for those
degrees of freedom that exist

An informational world of an
observer within the universe.
There is only one single eigenstate
for every defined degree of
freedom. This means that once a
particle is measured as having a
property it always has that
property relative to that observer
because it has already been
measured by the observer.

The diagrams above represent how informational spaces exist relative to the infinite whole, a universe within the infinite whole and the informational world of a single observer within that universe. This shows how both “infinite and finite ranges of informational degrees of freedom and eigenstates” define each of these 3 classes.

Limits of the Universe

Now it is fair to ask how the universe itself can be “finite” in the first place. After all, how could it “begin” and “end”? What would exist past its borders? This is to say that obviously there must be something that exists past the universes borders as it could not just “end”. Would there be other universes past these borders or simply nothing at all?

The answer is that the universe itself is defined relative to the observers inside of it. This means that the universe is not infinite because since there is a maximum speed of light, there must also be limits as to what observers within the universe can interact with. Therefore, anything that is “outside” of what observers could possibly interact with, would not exist as part of the universe since the universe is only defined by what observers could interact with. For example, any entity that is smaller in size than a “Planck Length” could not exist within this universe since it could never not be measured and observable to an observer. This is because if one tries to measure an entity smaller than a Planck Length, the amount of energy required to be placed in such a small

space would need to cause a black hole. This means that entities smaller than a Planck length could never be observable to observers so therefore can never “exist” within the universe that is defined by what is reachable to observers. This shows how “limits” within the universe can exist without it being infinite. The infinite whole however would not have such limitations (like a smallest or largest possible entity) since it exists not relative to observers but objectively. Therefore, it could not even have any possible separations of itself and “entities within it” in the first place, let alone some that are larger and smaller than others.

Now the reason that the “universe” would need to be defined relative to observers is simply because it is itself “subjective” and not “objective”. Again, this is because the infinite whole can have no objective separations. Therefore any separations of the infinite whole must exist not objectively in the context of the infinite whole but totally subjectively according to only their own contexts.

This means that the universe itself is a “limited finite box of information” within the infinite whole that itself results from the scope of what its observer can possibly interact with. This suggests that perhaps there can be a larger universe where observers could interact with information depending on certain “limitations” of that larger universe. A single observer within that universe could then theoretically “experience” observations in that larger universe that are only defined relative to what that particular observer can interact with in that larger universe. That observers observations would then themselves have to exist as a “limited range of informational entities degrees of freedoms and eigenstates”. This “range” of informational entities can then be described as a “sub-universe” of a larger universe.

What are Observers?

This would mean that a universe itself is defined by the amount of information that exists inside of it. This information that exists inside of the universe and defines it, would then be determined by what the observer who is observing the universe can interact with and observe. These limitations stem from the observer's parent universe which itself has a limited amount of information that defines what that parent observer can interact with. Every observers individual set of possible observations within that universe would be a universe of “informational states” in of itself. My hypothesis is that our universe is one of these “universes” formed by the limited observations of an observer in a parent universe.

Now what are observers? Observers would be entities within a universe that themselves are capable of observing “informational entities”. This means that they are essentially “information processing systems” that could collect information and measure said information. This is to say that when an observer observes a “universe”, within that universe there are information processing systems that themselves “help” the observer make measurable observations. For example, observers in this universe use “neural networks” within their brains to make observations and measurements of the world outside of them. These “neural networks” are essentially information processing systems that process information of the world relative to their own informational existences. They essentially “help” the observer who observes the universe which they are in, “measure” and “probe” the world outside of them.

In this sense, my hypothesis would be that “consciousness” itself is a result of information processing systems within a larger observers universe “individually experiencing” segmented parts of the parent observers consciousness through their ability to collect outside information and therefore information about themselves as well. This would mean that every observer that exists within a universe is a “measuring device” of a parent observer that observes the universe into existence. These observers then themselves experience an underlining “sense of being” simply because they each are a part of the parent observer’s consciousness. An example of this could be likened to a man using a camera. The camera records observations of what it itself is probing and even contains information related to what it has observed inside of it. However the “photographer” and the one who views and experiences that information cannot be found in the camera. This is because the camera itself is simply a measuring device used by the photographer. The photographer is not “inside” the camera but simply utilizes it to make observations. My hypothesis is that the parent observer of this universe uses “measuring devices” such as brains in order to collect information about the universe that the observer could interact with. These measuring devices thereby “segment” the parent observers consciousness into only viewing and experiences what those individual measuring devices can interact with. However, the underlying sense of being beneath those measuring devices would be the “whole” sense of being that stems from the observer utilizing them.

Summary:

- The infinite whole has an infinite amount of information and is not limited
- There is a universe that itself has a finite amount of information and is limited
- That universe has laws that are defined by the finite amount of information in that universe (such as how our universe has laws that are defined by the amount of information inside of it - speed of light, planck length etc)
- Within that universe there are measuring devices that are capable of “probing” parts of the universe which they are in (such as brains)
- These measuring devices each have their own individual “observational worlds” that come about based on what they measure (the individual “world” of information within each brain)
- These observational worlds are themselves “sub-universes” (every “world” inside of a brain is a universe).
- These measuring devices therefore observe parts of their universes and themselves make subjective “sub-universes” that are defined by the information that they individually observe. They are therefore observers and observe “sub-universes” into existence. (Every world inside of every brain is itself a universe).
- Observers individual consciousnesses are therefore tied to measuring devices because they essentially are “measuring devices” being used by a parent observer of their universe. (Brains are measuring devices used by the parent observer who observes the universe into existence).
- This parent observer uses them to measure their own universe which they are in. (Brains are the parent observers measuring devices that are used in order to investigate their own universe).
- The consciousness that every observer feels is the “collective consciousness” of their entire universe (the consciousness of the parent observer). The only reason it feels segmented to them is because the measuring devices that defines them can only collect a limited amount of information that exists relative to itself subjectively. It is therefore a “context” of the

“content” that is its whole universe. Consciousness is therefore experienced collectively while informational worlds are experienced individually so give an illusion that the consciousness is also experienced individually.

Note that this is simply a tentative hypothesis on ultimate reality and in no way what I consider to be the true nature of the universe’s ontology. It is rather a “model” of the universe that given my current knowledge can act as a formidable schema. I’m sure that in the future this schema of the universe and objective reality will undoubtedly refine and change.